

Chemical Investigation of *Cassia siamea* Lamk. Flowers and Bark

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CASSIA siamea Lamk. flowers have been found to contain D-pinitol, β -sitosterol, lupeol and four compounds, m.p. 205-6°, 207-8°, 212-14°, 216-17° of which first three are phenolic in nature. The flowers also contain sucrose, glucose, fructose and traces of arabinose in free form and two oligosaccharides, one consisting of glucose and arabinose while the second glucose, xylose, arabinose and glucuronic acid. The trunk bark of this plant has been found to contain β -sitosterol, lupeol and oleanolic acid and considerable amount of sucrose.

Cassia siamea Lamk. commonly known as "Kassod" belongs to family Leguminosae, sub-family Caesalpiniceae.

The heart wood of this plant has been investigated in the early 20th Century and is reported to contain chrysophanhydranthrone¹ where a toxic alkaloid² has been isolated from the pods. Chatterjee³ *et al.* have reported three dianthroquinone pigments viz. cassiamin, siameanin and siameadin in addition to betulin, betulinic acid, lupeol, lupeonone and a neutral compound m.p. 168-70° from trunk bark whereas Venkataraman *et al.*⁴ have reported cassiamin A, B, C from root bark. The heart wood has been reported to contain stilbenetrol⁵. The leaves and flowers have recently been studied and are reported to contain barakol⁶ and chromone⁷ respectively.

a) Study of Flowers :

The flowers collected from the Institute campus were dried and exhausted with ethanol. The ethanol extract after concentration gave a dark greenish mass which was extracted with petroleum ether. The petroleum ether extract after concentration was chromatographed on a column of silica gel.

The petroleum ether fractions (11-19) on crystallization from benzene-acetone gave colourless needles, m.p. 208-9°, acetate m.p. 212° identified as lupeol. The fractions 29-37 (petroleum ether - benzene 80 : 20) gave a colourless crystalline compound, m.p. 131-32° identified as β -sitosterol.

The fraction obtained by extraction of ethanol extract with acetone, on chromatography on a column of silica gel using benzene and acetone (95 : 5) gave four compounds.

Compound A m.p. 205-6°, acetate m.p. 132-34° and B m.p. 207-8°, acetate m.p. 192-3° gave pinkish violet

colour with ferric chloride showing their phenolic nature. Compound C m.p. 212-14° gave also pink colour with ferric chloride and positive Molish test. On hydrolysis with 6% hydrochloric acid on water bath gave an aglycone m.p. 243-44° which showed the tests for flavones. The hydrolysate gave only glucose. Therefore it seems to be the flavone glucoside. Compound D crystallized as light coloured cubes had m.p. 216-17°.

The residue left after acetone extraction was dissolved in methanol and on standing afforded colourless crystals m.p. 187°, $[\alpha]_D + 64^\circ$. It was identified as D-pinitol (lit. m.p. 187°, $[\alpha]_D + 65^\circ$) by m.p., m.m.p. and comparison of IR spectrum with authentic sample.

The mother liquor left after removal of pinitol showed the absence of saponin and presence of sugars which were identified as sucrose, glucose and fructose and traces of arabinose.

The ethanol exhausted flowers on extraction with water and purification gave a light coloured powder which showed the presence of two oligosaccharides on paper chromatography having very slow mobility. These were separated by preparative paper chromatography and hydrolysed with 2*N* sulphuric acid. The hydrolysate showed the presence of glucose and arabinose in one oligosaccharide and four sugars glucuronic acid, glucose, arabinose and xylose in case of the other oligosaccharide.

(b) Study of the Trunk Bark :

The fresh trunk bark of this plant was extracted with 80% aqueous ethanol. The ethanol extract on concentration gave a brown solid which separated on standing. The filtrate was diluted with little amount of water and successively extracted with ether.

The concentrated ether extract showed the presence of a number of compounds and therefore, was chromatographed on silica gel column. This gave following three compounds which have been identified as lupeol m.p. 209-11°, acetate m.p. 214°, β -sitosterol m.p. 131-32°, acetate m.p. 124-25° and oleanolic acid m.p. 308-9°, acetate m.p. 268° (lit. oleanolic acid m.p. 310°, acetate m.p. 268°) by m.m.p. and TLC.

The aqueous extract was extracted with *n*-butanol and the residual aqueous extract was concentrated and left in aqueous methanol for two days. This gave cubes which on recrystallization had m.p. 182-4° and identified as sucrose.

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References

1. K. IWAKAWA, *Arch. Exp. Path. Pharm.*, 1911, 65, 315-24.

NOTES

- A. H. WELLS, *Philippine J. Sc.*, 1919, 14, 1-7.
- A. CHATTERJEE and S. R. BHATTACHARYA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1964, 41, 415; *Bull. Nat. Inst. Sci.*, (India) 1965, 31, 141-50; A. CHATTERJEE, R. MUKHERJEE, S. K. SRIMANY and S. BHATTACHARYA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1966, 43, 63-4.
- K. VENKATARAMAN, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1966, 25(3), 97-118; N. L. DUTTA, A. C. GHOSH and K. VENKATARAMAN, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1964, 3023-30; V. P. PATIL, A. V. R. RAO and K. VENKATARAMAN, *Ind. J. Chem.*, 1970, 8(2), 109-12.
- C. M. D. UPADHYAY and L. NARENDRA, *Ind. J. Appl. Chem.*, 1968, 31, 239.
- W. B. BYEROFT and A. HASSANALI WALJI, A. W. JOHNSON and T. J. KING, *J. Chem. Soc. C.*, 1970, 1686-9.
- S. ARORA, H. DEYMANN, R. D. TIWARI and E. WINTERFIELD, *Tetrahedron*, 1971, 27, 981-5.

Some Experiments in the Friedel-Craft Reaction with Methyl- β -Resorcyrate

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FRIEDEL-Craft butyrylation of methyl β -resorcyrate(I) has been reported¹ to yield methyl 2,4-dihydroxy-3-butyryl benzoate(II), m.p. 69°, and methyl 2,4-dihydroxy-5-butyryl benzoate(III), m.p. 90°, and the

We also studied the valerylation and caproylation of (I) under Friedel-Craft conditions. Equimolecular amounts of (I) and corresponding acid chlorides were heated with 3 moles of anhydrous $AlCl_3$ in nitrobenzene for 4 hours. In both the cases, the corresponding 3- and 5-acyl esters were obtained which were separated by fractional crystallisation from petroleum ether. The less soluble compound was the *-* isomer. The esters were colourless crystalline solids and were characterised by the formation of 2,4-DNP derivatives. The structures of the compounds were established by their alkaline hydrolysis to the corresponding benzoic acids crystallised from dil. EtOH, which were decarboxylated either by heating with 10% NaOH for 4 hours (in case of 3-acyl acids) or boiling with quinoline and copper powder (in case of 5-acyl acids) to the known acyl resorcinol derivatives²⁻⁵.

The Friedel-Craft reaction of I with *p*-toluoyl chloride also yielded the corresponding 3- and 5-substituted esters, separated by fractional crystallisation from alcohol. Hydrolysis of the esters with cold alkali (10% NaOH) afforded the corresponding toluoyl benzoic acids which were decarboxylated by boiling with alkali (4 hrs.) to known resorcinol derivatives⁶. The latter were also obtained directly from the esters by boiling with alkali under the above conditions (Table).

All the compounds gave satisfactory elemental analysis.

Acid chloride	Esters obtained/solvent	Yield	M.P.	2,4-DNP M.P.	M.P. of the benzoic acid
<i>n</i> -Valerylchloride	1) Methyl-2, 4-dihydroxy-5-valeryl benzoate (EtOH)	(20)	58-59°	230-31°	175°
	2) Methyl-2, 4-dihydroxy-3-valeryl benzoate (EtOH)	(10)	48-50°	175°	154-55°
<i>n</i> -Caproylchloride	3) Methyl-2, 4-dihydroxy-5-caproyl benzoate (dil. EtOH)	(5)	54-55°	230°	180-81°
	4) Methyl-2, 4-dihydroxy-3-caproyl benzoate (dil. EtOH)	(3)	47-48°	222-23°	138-39°
<i>p</i> -Toluoylchloride	5) Methyl-2, 4-dihydroxy-5-toluoyl benzoate (EtOH)	(17)	148-49°	270-71°	227-28°
	6) Methyl-2, 4-dihydroxy-3-toluoyl benzoate (glacial HAc)	(15)	191-92°	156-57°	220-21°

m.p. of the DNP derivatives of II and III have been reported to be 270° and 283° respectively. We find the m.p.s. are as under: II, 92-93°, III, 86-87°, DNP of II, 195°, DNP of III, 262-64°.

References

- R. D. DESAI, B. M. DESAI and J. I. DESAI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1960, 37, 491.